

Evaluation of Live Video Streaming Performance for Low Latency Use Cases in 5G

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Abstract—This paper introduces the practical evaluation setup of the low latency video streaming system for extensive performance measurements using 5G test network. The results gathered with the latest 5G new radio indoor equipment enriched with the optimized streaming solutions and accurate measurement system reveal the bottlenecks in the mobile transmission path especially in uplink channel, and help to identify the places of improvement. These places of optimization are essential in the live low latency streaming scenarios of the different industries moving to wireless technologies in vehicle-based connectivity, such as streaming vital information from an ambulance to a receiving hospital, transmitting highly prioritized traffic or road information to other drivers, or streaming through congested mobile network in need of rapid adaptation. Furthermore, the experimental knowledge gained during the extensive measurements in real 5G test environment have demonstrated the application-based processing delay to have substantial effect on the total end-to-end latency. The ongoing 5G standardization and its actualization by the operators already enables enhanced mobile broadband and ultra-reliable low-latency communication for extreme high throughput and low latency streaming, but practical field research and evaluation is needed especially for sending time critical data to uplink direction from moving vehicles in the harsh signal environment. For better understanding of the requirements in low latency video streaming and planning the actual vehicle to network scenarios over 5G, it is essential to identify the current performance and possible restrictions before shifting to more complex system development.

Keywords—Live video streaming; Low latency; RTMP; RTSP; RTP; 5G NR

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of the fifth generation (5G) mobile networks has enabled evaluation and testing of low latency applications in harsh mobile environment. More and more of the 5G use cases are introduced in new industry areas relying purely on wireless networking, such as vehicle communications, surveillance, and healthcare [1]. These use cases can benefit from live video streaming scenarios in various ways, which emphasize the enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) and ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) set of features provided by 5G. In such scenarios, video streaming is expected to have high throughput (quality) with extremely low end-to-end (e2e) latency. One general scenario is the remote wireless access to working facilities, which can include live remote monitoring of the traffic from a vehicle, surroundings of the factory, or a patient in a moving ambulance. As a consequence the mobile traffic will continue its growth in the following years as the number of devices, users, and connections are expected

to increase [2], which means that more and more of testing is needed in actual operating environments.

This work sets up the baseline for our upcoming development and evaluation of low latency mobile video streaming in 5G, where the scene can include use of multiple cameras and more mobility demanding requirements even at high velocities. Such technology is beneficial in healthcare where live streaming is needed from moving ambulance relying simply on mobile network connectivity [3] [4], in mobile video surveillance [5], in vehicular connections for improving road safety services [6], and monitoring and remote control of autonomous devices [7]. The earlier experiments conducted using 5G test network (5GTN) [8] introduced already low latency streaming measurements, but focused on using 360-degree camera and hypertext transfer protocol (HTTP)-based adaptive streaming technologies targeted on larger audience. Streaming protocols like real-time messaging protocol (RTMP) [9] and real-time streaming protocol (RTSP)/real-time transport protocol (RTP) [10] are traditionally dedicated to be used for low latency video streaming. The advantage of RTSP/RTP and RTMP streaming protocols reduce the latency caused by the video segmentation in the HTTP streaming and can therefore decrease the needed buffering e.g. in the playback device. Some of the recent works have evaluated these streaming techniques in prior 5G scenarios [11]. RTMP works on top of transmission control protocol (TCP) which maintains persistent connection and makes it reliable to transmit all the video content to clients. RTSP is a application-level protocol for controlling the multimedia delivery in the networks using RTP as a network protocol for delivering multimedia in the networks. Usually RTP works on top of user datagram protocol (UDP), but it also enables its use on top of TCP in order to have easier access configuration through firewalls and network address translation (NAT)s especially in mobile long-term evolution (LTE) and 5G networking, for example.

The definition of latency in end-to-end video streaming is the delay when a video frame is captured by a camera until it appears on the display. There are several steps in this process where the main steps are capture, encoding, transmission, decoding, and display. Each step adds some delay and the sum of the delays is the e2e latency. In [12] is presented a video communication chain model, where all components that influence e2e latency have been introduced. In the video processing some amount of data needs to be buffered for a short time which causes latency. The amount of data buffering can vary from pixels to several video lines or even to several frames. For instance, a delay of one frame in

30 frames-per-second (fps) video corresponds 33.3 ms latency. The transmission latency is depending on the used network. In the mobile networks delay is typically from milliseconds to tens of milliseconds but delay varies (jitter) when packets arrive to the receiver with different delays. If each packet is played out immediately, the video playback speed will fluctuate or even stop. A smoother playback requires buffering for the incoming packets, which introduces more latency. A longer buffer eliminates the effects of jitter, but increases latency.

In this paper we present our system for the low latency video streaming and its performance measurements using 5G test network. Section II presents the system architecture in conjunction with the 5G test network. In Section III, we illustrate the setup for evaluating the low latency streaming scenarios towards more efficient mobile streaming. Section IV presents the results of the evaluation and finally in Section V, conclusion is done.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The live low latency video streaming system architecture contains a Video Camera, an Encoder, a Video Server located at the edge, and a Video Player. The architecture is suitable for several use cases for different industries. Our areas of interests are healthcare, critical communications, monitoring and remote control of mobile machinery, where live streaming is required relying only on a mobile connection. The overview of the system architecture is presented in Fig. 1. The modern video cameras capable for live streaming usually either contain the encoder and the streaming server within the camera, or can have wired HDMI/USB connectivity to the Encoder. For higher 4K/8K resolutions, the use of video capture cards is recommended. The Encoder can be hardware (HW) or software (SW) based and it is responsible for compressing the video from the Video Camera using the desired encoding settings e.g. defining the format, resolution, frame rate, before publishing/sending the video using desired protocol to the Video Server.

The next block 'Network' in Fig. 1 contains the uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) network connection. In mobile network where live streaming is applied, UL connection basically defines the stream quality and maximum video bitrate since it is usually less prioritized in terms of channel throughput whereas DL is configured to have higher capacity. In general level, 5G (TDD) frame structure allocation defines the shares between UL and DL, which is usually configured to 1/4 or 3/7 UL/DL shares. Naturally, mobile users are consuming more DL channel in their daily activities. Usually in large events before 5G era the content UL delivery was using wired local area network (LAN) connection either via ethernet or fiber because of the speed and reliability. However, more and more of the industries are willing to shift from wired technologies to wireless in order to gain faster and uncomplicated physical setup.

The Video Server part in the architecture is the first processing node after the Encoder and can be in charge of a) streaming the video either functioning as a streaming server or as a web server, b) transcoding the video to one or multiple representations, c) functioning as a proxy. As the Video Server is located on the edge of mobile network it operates as multi

Fig. 1: The system architecture for low latency video streaming.

access edge computing (MEC), which is also important in the big picture in terms of latency: selecting dynamically the nearest MEC can have a reduction in the e2e latency. For example, the popular content can be cached or transcoded near the users. In our work, the Video Server is used as RTSP and RTMP streaming server, which receives the video from the Encoder and serves the video to the Video Player.

Finally, the Video Player is in charge of receiving, decoding, and playback the content via DL from the Video Server. Multiple devices and applications exist with their unique processing capabilities and HW/SW characteristics. The dedicated video applications can introduce different levels of delay originating only in the client device. The Video Player usually has network or application level buffering (or both), which can increase the experienced latency. Thus, majority of the current video players are equipped with low latency options that affect especially to the buffering.

In our setup for this architecture, a live 4K web Camera is connected to the video Encoder through a USB cable. The Encoder is connected to the 5GTN, which will be presented in the next Section. The Encoder encodes the live video stream feed using x264 software encoder with low latency settings and publishes the stream to Video server. The Video Server is located at the edge server of 5GTN and it contains the RTMP server and the RTSP server. The RTMP server receives the live video feed and serves the stream to the Video Player using TCP protocol. The RTSP server receives the live video feed and serves video the stream to the Video Player using either UDP or TCP protocol. The Video Player is connected to the 5GTN and it plays the video from the Video Server.

III. EVALUATION

This section presents the test setup and the test cases for the low latency live video streaming system that utilizes the system architecture illustrated in Fig. 1.

A. Measurement setup

The evaluation setup was built in the 5GTN [13] test environment, which is a Finnish mobile network test site located and maintained at the premises of VTT and University of Oulu. The 5GTN has a wide set of different features to be tested including several evolved packet core (EPC) alternatives ranging from pure SW simulators running on a laptop to actual cloud mobility management core running on a rack server. The network infrastructure contains also several servers and options e.g. for MEC and evolved multimedia broadcast multicast service (eMBMS), which both are supportive features in live

video streaming experiments in the mobile environment. The radio part for small cells comprises the latest LTE and cellular internet of things (CIoT) cells operating under 3 GHz, and 5G new radio (NR) indoor small cells (3.6 GHz) with outdoor massive multiple in multiple out (MIMO) (3.6 GHz) cells both operating on frequency band n78 (see also Table I). In this work, we used only indoor 5G small cells for the evaluation, which rely on time-division duplex (TDD) communication on 3/7 frame structure allocation for UL and DL.

The low latency video streaming test cases are listed in Table II. In addition to comparison between the LAN baseline and the 5G measurements (test cases 1-4), we wanted especially to see how additional UL traffic influences to UL and e2e delays. This scenario is relatively realistic in nowadays multi-angle streaming scenarios when multiple camera feeds congest the network in the area of same small cell (test cases 5-6). The iPerf3 tool [14] was used for generating additional TCP traffic with another laptop, connected to the same UL access point as the Encoder. In these experiments we were purely interested on congesting the same subscriber connection as the Encoder is using.

During the pre-testing for the low latency system architecture, we also evaluated the live streaming RTSP/RTP over UDP instead of TCP. RTSP/RTP protocol enables the use of both these network protocols and during the pre-testing two notable observations was made: First, the e2e latency over wired LAN was similar when comparing UDP and TCP. Secondly, we faced NAT and/or firewall problem when streaming over 5G, which emphasized the decision to evaluate TCP-based streaming in all test cases.

The test setup is based on open source software and the overview is presented in Fig. 2 and the most essential video parameters in Table I. All the servers/computers run on Ubuntu 18.04 operating system. The Logitech BRIO 4K Ultra HD Pro webcam is connected via USB cable to the Lenovo Core i7 laptop, which performs as the video Encoder. In practical detailed measurements in different heterogeneous networks, such as in ours, the wired camera connection is preferred in order have better flexibility to use third-party applications for reliable network measurements, especially in terms of delay. The accurate measuring requires not only the software node installation in the sender, but also exact timing synchronization between the network nodes.

The SW video Encoder is based on FFmpeg [15] framework, which captures the full HD video through the USB port in YUV format and compresses the video using x264 encoder with 4 Mbit/s target bitrate and following low latency settings: *preset=ultrafast, tune=zerolatency, profile=main, bframes=0, ref=3, scenecut=0*. Full HD resolution is realistic for our use cases and preliminary evaluation without the need of HW acceleration during encoding. The Encoder is connected to

TABLE I: Video and network parameters.

Video		Network	
Resolution	1920x1080 (Full HD)	Wired network	1 Gbps Ethernet
Bitrate	4 Mbit/s	5G NR BS	gNB small cell @ 3.6 GHz
Frame rate	30 fps	5G Frequency	Band n78 @ 60 MHz
Coding/encoder	H.264/x264	5G EPC version	Nokia EPC simulator

TABLE II: Test cases.

Test case	Streaming protocol	Network type	Network protocol	Other traffic
1	RTMP	Wired/LAN	TCP	No
2	RTSP/RTP	Wired/LAN	TCP	No
3	RTMP	5G	TCP	No
4	RTSP/RTP	5G	TCP	No
5	RTMP	5G	TCP	Yes (TCP)
6	RTSP/RTP	5G	TCP	Yes (TCP)

the network using either LAN or 5G connection depending on the test case. The Encoder streams the video to the Video Server via RTMP or RTSP/RTP depending on the test case. In all the test cases the video is pushed to the Video Server over TCP. The Video Server at the edge contains both RTMP server (Nginx with rtmp-module [16]) and RTSP server (rtsp-simple-server [17]). RTMP or RTSP server receives the video feed from the Encoder and streams the video over TCP to the Video Player, which is a powerful laptop with Ubuntu 18.04 and Intel Core i9 processor running the MPV [18] player application.

For the 5G connectivity, two Huawei customer price equipment (CPE) access points was used both in the Encoder as well as in the Video Player, which connected to 5GTN via SIM cards. For the test cases 5 and 6, another laptop was connected to the UL CPE, which generated the additional traffic using iPerf3. The possible interference from other users was relatively easy to accomplish since majority of the 5GTN users were at remote working.

B. Measurement tools

In order to verify the functionality and performance of the low latency live video streaming system, and to resolve the bottlenecks in the system causing delay, we performed measurements using two methods: 1) measurements using screen clock capturing and 2) measurements with network performance indicator Qosium.

In the first method the Video Camera captures the current time in milliseconds from a Screen 1. The Video Player plays the video in a Screen 2 that is next to the Screen 1. We take a picture of the screens and calculate the time difference, which is defined as the end-to-end latency. We used the MPV player version 0.33.0 [18] in the client for the playback and display in the Screen 2. The MPV player was launched with low latency profile that reduces the experienced latency alongside with *untimed* flag that reduces the timing latency. The refresh rate of the Screen 1 is 60 Hz and the Encoder frame rate is 30 fps. This means that the time precision on the Screen 1 is 16.7 ms and on the Encoder 33.3 ms. The measurement method precision is approximately 50 ms, which is relatively large compared to the total e2e latency. Hence enough the measurements should be made several times and averaged to obtain a more reliable results. Also the precision must be taken into account when analyzing the results.

In the second method Qosium [19] was used for measuring the UL and DL network performance as it can provide a real-time, passive, and lightweight packet capturing method using pcap libraries for reliable measurement without generating additional traffic into the network. Qosium consists of two parts: Probe and Scope. The Probes are installed in different nodes in the network, such as in laptops or PC servers, network

Fig. 2: Evaluation setup.

switches, or mobile devices running on Android. The Scope is responsible for visualizing and/or gathering the results from the primary and secondary measurement Probes depending on the traffic direction. It is not necessary for the Scope to be part of the measurement path as it requires only network connection to one of the Probes.

Fig. 2 shows the Probe nodes in the verification cases. The UL measurement path holds the Probes in the Encoder and the Video Server, and DL measurement holds the Probes in the Video Server and the Video Player, respectively. The Scope was placed on a separate laptop for gathering the results, connected to the Probe located in the Video Server. In the measurements, delay, and throughput are the main indicators visualized in the results. Thus, indicators such as packet loss, and delay jitter were also monitored, but left outside the scope of the results.

Accurate time synchronization is critical for LAN and 5G measurements, since one-way delays under 10 ms are reality. We use precision time protocol (PTP) daemon [20] for the synchronization between different machines as illustrated in Fig. 2. One PTP master is located in 5GTN, performing basically as an edge server to which PTP slaves sync their clocks. The interconnection for time synchronization is implemented by using wired network interface in each machine whereas the video data is carried by using another wired network interface via CPE access points.

IV. RESULTS

This section illustrates the results of our selected test cases presented in Table II. We first measured the 5G capacity several times using both Speedtest as well as iPerf3 resulting to approximately 50 Mbit/s and 650 Mbit/s for UL and DL maximum throughputs, respectively. In the first subsection, we present the results comparing the network delay and e2e latency between RTMP and RTSP/RTP streaming. The second subsection consists of the results when additional traffic was added into network. The red graph 'Live stream throughput' in Fig. 5 shows the average bitrate for the evaluated live video stream. The bitrate stays very constant in the average of 4 Mbit/s, thanks to accurate rate control in x264 encoder.

A. RTMP vs RTSP/RTP latency

As depicted in previous Section, Qosium was used to measure accurate network delays for all the test cases. The Qosium measurements both in UL and DL were the averages of 10 runs each with the duration of 60 s. The variation between runs was surprisingly small, because number of interfering mobile users was very small and video bitrate was staying constant when recording only the screen of the digital clock.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 combine the results for test cases 1-4. The UL and DL averages for the LAN measurements were between 0.2 and 0.3 ms for the both streaming protocols. The RTSP/RTP averages for 5G were 12.6 ms (UL) and 5.6 ms (DL) and similarly 12.4 ms (UL) and 7.3 (DL) for RTMP. As can be seen the delay variation between min-max values is very small: 1.1 ms for RTSP/RTP and 1.5 ms for RTMP.

We measured the e2e latency which is the time difference between a timer captured in the Screen 1 until it is displayed on the Screen 2. In the video streaming system the e2e latency is the total delay caused by capturing in the camera, encoding, network delivery to the UL to the video server, processing at the video server, network delivery to DL to the video player, and playback. Each measurement took 120 s and we took a picture of the screens every five seconds. Based on the pictures we calculated the e2e latency.

Fig. 6 shows the average values for the e2e latency for RTMP and RTSP/RTP streaming. The baseline e2e latency has been measured in wired LAN network without additional traffic. The 5G measurements with '0' traffic represents the comparative values. The difference between LAN and 5G is very small and total e2e delay is well under 200 ms.

B. Impact of congestion

The test cases 5-6 are done by congesting the 5G UL network with additional traffic. As stated earlier, we wanted to see the effect to the evaluated live stream especially when the same subscriber connection of which the Encoder is using gets congested. This is a relevant use case when multiple cameras are connected to the same encoder, such as inside a vehicle enabling remote driving. The result graphs do not include DL

Fig. 3: Measured average RTSP/RTP delay for the live video stream.

delays measured with Qosium, since they are similar as the curves presented in Fig. 3 and in Fig. 4, because DL was not congested in these test cases.

The blue curve 'Total traffic load' in Fig. 5 visualizes the total 5G traffic output measured as the input volume in the Video Server by Qosium. It comprises both video stream as well as generated additional traffic from iPerf3 with values of 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 Mbit/s taking place in corresponding values as seconds in the timeline (x-axis). This is the reason why the evaluation time is longer compared to other test cases. As can be seen, the UL capacity is approximately 50 Mbit/s as stated in the beginning of this Section. The small downward peaks occurring at 50 s and 60 s happen because iPerf3 has a small lag in the re-launching process, when a new target bitrate is introduced to the iPerf3 client.

Fig. 7 shows the whole UL delay for RTSP/RTP and RTMP measured with Qosium. Fig. 8 illustrates the magnification of the graph between 0-60 s in order to have more detailed view of the delay before congestion is too severe. We observe that lower traffic under 30 Mbit/s increases the UL delay only slightly, approximately 2.5 ms. This is still in an acceptable level, even at 30-40 Mbit/s where delay stays in under 20ms. The final congestion at 40-50 Mbit/s is too much and unacceptable causing the delay increase as high as 400 ms.

Fig. 6 presents the e2e latency with additional traffic. We can see from the figure that latency increases slightly when additional traffic on the network is added. When additional

Fig. 4: Measured average RTMP delay for the live video stream.

Fig. 5: Measured average throughputs for RTMP and RTSP/RTP stream and for total traffic.

traffic is 50 Mbit/s the uplink is congested and e2e latency is over 500 ms which is usually too much in many use cases. The experienced latency in this case is caused by the TCP re-transmissions. After the traffic is normalized, the Video Player catches up the lag in the playback at the original level.

These were the results of our experiments. The e2e latency as well as network UL/DL delay difference between usage of RTMP and RTSP/RTP was very small over TCP. Small error factor in screen clock capturing originates with the synchronization between display refresh rate, video frame rate, and camera capture. Thus, the averaging of the values seemed to generate reasonable results. The variation in e2e latency was slightly larger than in network measurements. But there are several factors causing this ranging from encoding-decoding characteristics to playback buffering and actual display. The exploitation of RTSP/RTP allows optionally UDP or TCP transmission, but NATs and firewalls can be a problem for UDP. Then again, RTMP works only over TCP but is integrated quite well with Nginx web server. From video player perspective, both seem to work equally well. The network delay measurements indicated that current version of 5G performs well even when UL channel gets congested. Thus, it needs to be concluded that current UL capacity both in current 5G NR is not sufficient when extremely high quality with high resolution, and bitrate is required to be transmitted over UL, such as in multiple camera scenarios.

Fig. 6: Measured end-to-end latency for RTMP and RTSP/RTP streaming with different volume of additional traffic.

Fig. 7: Measured average uplink delay for the evaluated live stream congested with additional traffic.

Fig. 8: Measured average uplink delay for the evaluated live stream congested with additional traffic - more detailed view.

V. CONCLUSION

This work presented the developed setup for low latency video streaming tests, and results conducted in 5GTN using 5G NR technology focusing on RTMP and RTSP based streaming on top of TCP. The extensive set of numerical results concerning both UL and DL network delays as well as experienced e2e latency starting from camera capture and ending to screen display in client video player, indicate that 5G radio link is extremely suitable wireless network to be used in low latency streaming. The sufficient UL capacity enables approximately 12 ms delay to edge server acting as the streaming server in our use case. When additional traffic e.g. by other users or multiple cameras is introduced in the area of same small cell, the delay still stays relatively decent level until 90-100% of the whole capacity is in use leading to higher delays. However, the valuable results and knowledge gained throughout the laboratory indoor experiments function as a basis before evaluating the performance in mobile outdoor environment introduced with velocity. Such measurements will be valuable for use cases that focus on healthcare and vehicle-based scenarios, where live streaming with low latency can form a vital factor for passing the live video content from the field or vehicle to the remote operator.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Ullah, N. Gopalakrishnan Nair, A. Moore, C. Nugent, P. Muschamp, and M. Cuevas, "5g communication: An overview of vehicle-to-everything, drones, and healthcare use-cases," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 37 251–37 268, 2019.
- [2] Cisco, "Cisco annual internet report (2018–2023) white paper," Cisco Public, Tech. Rep., 2020.
- [3] I. U. Rehman, M. M. Nasralla, A. Ali, and N. Philip, "Small cell-based ambulance scenario for medical video streaming: A 5g-health use case," in *2018 15th International Conference on Smart Cities: Improving Quality of Life Using ICT IoT (HONET-ICT)*, 2018, pp. 29–32.
- [4] I. U. Rehman, N. Y. Philip, and R. S. H. Istepanian, "Performance analysis of medical video streaming over 4g and beyond small cells for indoor and moving vehicle (ambulance) scenarios," in *2014 4th International Conference on Wireless Mobile Communication and Healthcare - Transforming Healthcare Through Innovations in Mobile and Wireless Technologies (MOBIHEALTH)*, 2014, pp. 211–216.
- [5] G. Gualdi, A. Prati, and R. Cucchiara, "Video streaming for mobile video surveillance," *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 1142–1154, 2008.
- [6] T. Ojanperä, J. Mäkelä, O. Mämmelä, M. Majanen, and O. Martikainen, "Use cases and communications architecture for 5g-enabled road safety services," in *2018 European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC)*, 2018, pp. 335–340.
- [7] H. Kokkonen-Tarkkanen, S. Horsmanheimo, A. Grudnitsky, M. Moisio, Z. Li, M. A. Uusitalo, D. Samardzija, T. Härkönen, and P. Yli-Paunu, "Enabling safe wireless harbor automation via 5g urllc," in *2019 IEEE 2nd 5G World Forum (5GWF)*, 2019, pp. 403–408.
- [8] M. Uitto and A. Heikkinen, "Exploiting and evaluating live 360° low latency video streaming using cmaf," in *2020 European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC)*, 2020, pp. 276–280.
- [9] M. T. H. Parmar, "Adobe's real time messaging protocol," Adobe Syst. Inc., Tech. Rep., 2012.
- [10] IETF, "Real time streaming protocol (rtsp)," RFC 2326, Tech. Rep., 1998.
- [11] A. Aloman, A. I. Ispas, P. Ciotirnae, R. Sanchez-Iborra, and M. D. Cano, "Performance evaluation of video streaming using mpeg dash, rtsp, and rtmp in mobile networks," in *2015 8th IFIP Wireless and Mobile Networking Conference (WMNC)*, 2015, pp. 144–151.
- [12] C. Bachhuber, E. Steinbach, M. Freundl, and M. Reisslein, "On the minimization of glass-to-glass and glass-to-algorithm delay in video communication," *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 238–252, 2018.
- [13] 5GTN. (2019) 5GTN - 5G test network. [Online]. Available: <https://5gtn.fi/>
- [14] iPerf3. (2021) iperf3. [Online]. Available: <https://iperf.fr/>
- [15] FFmpeg. (2021) Ffmpeg multimedia framework. [Online]. Available: <https://ffmpeg.org/>
- [16] R. Arutyunyan. (2017) Nginx rtmp-module. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/arut/nginx-rtmp-module>
- [17] A. Ros. (2021) Rtspsimple server. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/aler9/rtsp-simple-server>
- [18] MPV. (2021) Mpv media player. [Online]. Available: <https://mpv.io/>
- [19] Kaitotek. (2020) Qosium. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaitotek.com/qosium>
- [20] K. Correll. (2020) Ptpd, precision time protocol daemon. [Online]. Available: <https://ptpd.sourceforge.net>